

Pedagogical and psychological possibilities of developing children's speech through sensory education

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Abstract: This article describes the pedagogical and psychological possibilities of developing the speech of children of preschool age, the ways and content of using methods that increase speech through sensory education in various activities.

Today, it is one of the most important tasks to raise the young generation to become mature people in all aspects. Because the development, social, political and economic well-being of any society depends on the intellectual and moral potential of citizens and their level of spirituality.

It is known that expressing thoughts and thinking is done through speech. The more a child's thinking is developed, the more perfect his ability to express his thoughts will be. Since each person has the responsibility to correctly express their thoughts and thoughts, the formation of these skills in young people should begin in preschool educational institutions. In this case, the use of sensory education is pedagogically convenient.

The results of the analysis of mental processes by many psychologists show that the development of a child's speech is a unique process. L.S. Vygotsky, A.N. Leontev, S.L. Rubinstein, According to P.P. Blonsky, A. Vallon, J. Piage and others, mental processes, especially the formation and development of perception, are their social experience, that is, experience expressed in the form of a system of sensory standards

collected and accepted by previous generations (A.V. Zaporozhets). arises as a result of active absorption.

Such standards can include music and speech sounds, geometric shapes, spectrum rays, etc. Each child acquires these standards during the educational process, and then uses them as sensory standards to absorb, analyze, understand the essence of the surrounding objects and events, and improve sensory experiences.

In psychology, perceptive actions (actions related to emotional perception), the structure of images, are interpreted as a mechanism for reflecting the objective characteristics of things and events in reality. The image of the object is imagined due to "simulation" and copying of these features (A.N. Leontev).

A number of works devoted to the study of personality perception (A.N. Leontev, A.V. Zaporozhets, B.G. Anan'ev, V.P. Zinchenko, L.A. Wenger) testify that sensory processes consist of specific guiding actions that contribute to the child's practical cognitive activity. serves.

In time, I.M. Sechenov described the cognitive process of preschool children and put forward the idea of reflex activity of the brain. In this, he relies on the ability of the psyche to reflect the objective world. The scientist explains that perceptions of objects are formed under the influence of external signals. In this case, the image of a certain object is reflected on the retina many times, tensing and moving the muscles.

The experience of actions based on the assessment of various forms is embodied under the influence of the combination of the visual factor and the sensation of muscles. The ability to correctly identify the shapes of different objects depends on this ability to evaluate. Children of the first age have little such experience. Shapes of objects are learned not only by sight, but also by touch.

L.A. Venger implemented the development of perception in primary and preschool children with the help of certain didactic tools. For this, the child should have the ability to search for, find, differentiate, equate objects, to understand the specific nature of objects, that is, to give an external description of things.

In addition, our ancestors taught the need to limit children as little as possible. If the child does not have enough conditions to learn all the features of a certain item, then it is necessary to form preliminary ideas about these items.

For this, it is necessary to clearly define the tasks of sensory education. It is advisable to do this in the following 3 directions:

1. Formation of observation skills in children;
2. Formation of sensory standards in children;
3. Achieving the inculcation of certain skills and standards in the child's daily activities.

It is clear that all three directions indicated above are closely related to each other. Perceptual skills are imprinted in memory in the commonly accepted form of additional concepts and benchmarks. Pedagogical-psychological observations show that the use of the process of sensory education in the development of the speech of children of preschool age allows to ensure their general intellectual development. The first stage of sensory education is aimed at serving as a foundation for the formation of concepts based on sensory experience: the existence that surrounds us, understanding of life, free thinking, etc. in preschool children.

Success in mental, moral, physical education depends on how much attention is paid to the development of children's speech by means of sensory education in preschool educational organizations, that is, their perception of words in connection with what

they see and hear, their environment they should be able to understand the events in the environment, express their opinion about them, imagine the meanings of the words they use.

As the child grows up, his influence on the things around him, his understanding of things, his imagination, and the skills of accepting the opinions of others improve. In this regard, the stage of growing up is effective in further psychological development and general understanding. The younger the child, the more important the level of feeling is in his life.

In the process of mastering the properties of things, in order to have a more complete picture of them, the child should learn to use mutually different properties of objects at the same time. 9/10 of the intellectual development of children of preschool age is made up of impressions perceived by feeling. The richer the child's senses and perception, the more formed their ideas about the environment.

The content and methods of sensory education are determined by how the problem of developing perception and intuition is interpreted in psychology. Science has different approaches to this problem. Because they direct children's emotions to a specific goal through a specific pedagogical system. The main goal of developing children's speech through sensory education is aimed at the rapid formation of their perceptions and the realization of their abilities. Sensory education is important for children to perceive objects and events more deeply, to feel them.

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